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Sustainable Valorization of Bauxite Residue (“Red Mud”): Exploring the Potential of H₂ Reduction for Multi-metal Recovery

Ganesh Pilla, Tobias Hertel, and Yiannis Pontikes

Abstract

This study presents a process for the simultaneous recovery of metals from bauxite residue (BR) at relatively lower temperatures using H₂ reduction to achieve zero-waste discharge (minimal waste generation) of BR. The proposed method involves blending BR with NaOH and subjecting it to H₂ reduction (using different process parameters), resulting in an intermediate material enriched in magnetite and water-soluble aluminate. Optimal process parameters were determined (temperature of 600 °C, a reduction time of 120 min, 20 wt.% NaOH addition, and a reduction atmosphere of 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ with a 20 L/h flowrate), resulting in satisfactory recoveries of Fe (74.7%, grade = 40%), Al (81.5%), and Na (91.4%). This approach represents a step towards the sustainable valorization of BR, i.e., the efficient recovery of metals (Fe, Al, and Na) along with a non-magnetic fraction (Ca, Si, Ti, Rare earth elements), a precursor for further Sc, Ti recovery, and an additive eventually for building materials.

Keywords

Bauxite residue • Red mud • Sustainability • Circular economy • Metal extraction • Hydrogen

Introduction

The production of alumina from bauxite results in the significant generation of bauxite residue (BR) or red mud, a substantial solid waste. About 1 to 2 tons of BR are typically produced for each ton of recovered alumina [1]. The

landfilling of substantial quantities of BR (>170 million tons/year) is associated with management risks, and occasionally even accidents, affecting both the environment and human lives. Globally, less than 3% of the BR is used, with the majority accumulated near the alumina refineries. BR is valued as a secondary resource rich in metals like Fe, Al, Na, Si, Ti, and REEs [2]. Yet, applying conventional beneficiation methods (gravity, magnetic, flotation techniques) for the recovery of these metals leads typically to poor recovery as BR is a complex material due to its intricate composition, small particle size, and high pH (>10).

Both pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical methodologies have been explored to recover valuable metals from BR, as indicated in previous studies [3, 11, 14, 15]. A pilot-scale pyrometallurgical process has been proposed for the production of high-grade pig iron (with a purity of 95%) and mineral wool using Greek BR as a feedstock. This process has the capacity to utilize 1300 tonnes of dry BR per month, yielding 300 tonnes of pig iron and 865 tonnes of mineral wool [3]. However, it should be noted that this process consumes a significant amount of energy, approximately 2000 kWh per ton, and faces challenges associated with the substantial use of flux and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. These factors may limit its practicality for large-scale industrial implementation. The establishment of a hydrometallurgical route for the production of high-purity magnetite (98%), alumina (98%), and titania (98%) from BR has been achieved at the laboratory scale [15]. The potential for upscaling this process to an industrial level hinges on the development of a comprehensive approach for adapting the intricate process routes, effective management of liquid byproduct waste, and the implementation of stringent safety protocols for handling hazardous acids and substances such as H₂SO₄, NH₄OH, and C₂H₂O₄.

Recent efforts have focused on the exploration of hydrogen reduction at low temperatures as a promising method for recovering metals from BR [4–10]. However, the limited existing literature addressing the recycling of substantial

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waste quantities raises uncertainties about the feasibility of upscaling such initiatives to achieve a sustainable BR process on an industrial scale.

Therefore, this study proposed a method for the simultaneous recovery of Fe (in the form of magnetite), Al, and Na along with non-magnetic fraction (Ca, Si, Ti, and REEs) from H₂ reduced intermediate products. Unlike the smelting/pyrometallurgical processes, this method involves a combination of low-temperature H₂ reduction (<700 °C) and subsequent combined water leaching-magnetic separation (at 60 °C). This method has the potential to offer a more sustainable, economically viable, and technologically feasible solution to address the need to upvalue BR for metal recovery. It can achieve lower energy consumption during the process, eliminate waste disposal issues, and significantly reduce the carbon footprint. The H₂ reduction is carried out at a reduction temperature of 400–700 °C for 30–120 min, and NaOH addition of 10–25 wt.% under 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ (flowrate = 20 L/h) atmosphere. The effect of different process parameters and phase formations is evaluated on the recovery of Fe, Al, and Na. The process parameters were optimized by employing response surface methodology (RSM) for simultaneous recovery of Fe, Al, and Na from H₂ reduced BR. This investigation ultimately provides valuable insights into optimizing and scaling up the recovery of Fe, Al, and Na from BR through a combined approach involving H₂ reduction and water leaching-magnetic separation.

Materials and Methods

Raw Materials

The bauxite residue (BR) utilized in this study was provided by Mytilineos S.A, Greece. Before being used in the experiments, the sample underwent drying at 110 °C for 12 h, till constant weight as a function of time was achieved, and was subsequently sieved through a 500 µm sieve, and mixed, in order to ensure homogenization. Analytical grade (purity > 99.9) sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was used as an additive to BR for H₂ reduction experiments. If the NaOH has impurities, it might affect the extraction efficiency of Aluminum. During water leaching-magnetic separation or wet-milling process, these impurities dissolve and impact the metallurgical-grade alumina production.

Experimental Procedure

The process begins with a pelletization (Eirich mixer type EL1) step in which 100 g of BR was blended with NaOH solution (with an addition of 10–25 wt.% based on dry

weight). The resulting pellets are within the size range of 10–20 mm and were subsequently dried. BR has a very fine particle size distribution and it's adequate to use this material in the pellet form for efficient utilization instead of fines and without losing the products. In addition, pellets are preferred for better metallurgical properties such as high reducibility and better permeability. A rectangular alumina boat-type crucible containing approximately 100 g of pellets was placed in a lab-scale box furnace under an N₂ atmosphere. H₂ gas (5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ with a flow rate of 20 L/h) was purged for a specified reduction time (30–120 min) and at a designated temperature (ranging from 400 to 700 °C). After the reduction process, the pellets were cooled to room temperature under an N₂ atmosphere (flowrate of 10 L/h) to prevent oxidation of the reduced pellets.

Following the reduction, wet grinding (Retsch RS200 model) of the pellets was carried out with a solid-to-liquid (S/L) ratio of 0.5. The resulting wet-milled slurry products were then subjected to water leaching and wet-magnetic separation. As compared to dry magnetic separation, wet-magnetic separation is suitable for fine particles in terms of efficient separation of different metals from BR along with enhancement of scalability. This separation process aimed to separate water-soluble aluminate solution (for Al and Na recovery), magnetic fraction (for Fe recovery), and non-magnetic products (consisting of Ca, Si, and Ti). Within the water-leaching setup, a solid magnet block (with a magnetic strength of 0.29 T) was positioned to facilitate the separation of the magnetic product from the non-magnetic portion. Water leaching was conducted at 60 °C, employing an S:L ratio of 1:10 to prevent Si-gel formation and enhance the effectiveness of Fe, Al, and Na recovery. After a 60-min water leaching period, the magnetic fraction was detached from the magnetic block. The remaining solid was separated from the leach liquor through a two-stage filtration process involving filter papers with pore sizes of 12 µm and 0.45 µm, respectively.

Product Characterization

The characteristics of the reduced products were assessed using Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (WDXRF) analysis performed with a 4 kW Bruker S9 Tiger instrument, Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) conducted with an S8 Varian 720 ES axial instrument, as well as X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis using a Bruker D2 Phaser instrument with Cu-K radiation within a 10–50° 2θ range and a 0.08 step size. The ICDD-PDF database was employed for XRD analysis. Additionally, the SEM-EDS (Scanning Electron Microscopy—Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy) technique

was employed using an XL 30 FEG instrument to examine the microstructural variation. To determine the recovery of Fe, Al, and Na, the formulas outlined in earlier studies [8] were adopted for calculation purposes.

Process Optimization

To determine the optimal parameters for simultaneous Fe, Al, and Na recovery and explore the impact of various process variables and their interrelationships, the study employed a design of experiments (DoE) approach. This approach involved utilizing statistical models [13] through the implementation of response surface methodology (RSM) performed using Design Expert JMP Pro software version 17. The specifics regarding DoE-RSM models are discussed elsewhere [13, 14]. The study examines three process factors, namely reduction temperature (x_1) ranging from 400 to 700 °C, reduction duration (x_2) ranging from 30 to 120 min, and NaOH addition level (x_3) ranging from 10 to 25 wt.%. In the laboratory, the prescribed number of experimental runs (Table 1), utilizing the DoE to include all possible combinations, were executed. For each experimental run, the recovery rates of Fe, Al, and Na were computed.

Table 1 Experimental matrix for reduction experiments of 5 vol% H₂ + 95 vol% N₂ with 20 L/h flowrate and recovery results of Fe, Al, and Na at different runs

Experiment	Variables			Response (experimental data on recovery, %)		
	Reduction temperature (°C) — $\times 1$	Reduction time (min)— $\times 2$	NaOH concentration (wt %)— $\times 3$	Fe	Al	Na
1	600	120	10	68.6	62.6	77.3
2	600	120	15	72.8	71.3	87.7
3	600	120	20	74.7	81.5	91.4
4	600	120	25	57	81.8	92.4
5	600	30	20	69.8	79.4	88.9
6	600	60	20	70.2	80.6	90.7
7	400	120	20	49.1	76.8	87.9
8	500	120	20	76.5	80.2	90.1
9	700	120	20	50.2	84.0	92
10	700	120	10	60.5	62.4	78.8
11	700	30	10	66.6	59.8	75.2
12	700	30	25	40.1	83.6	89.4
13	400	30	10	34.5	59.8	82.8

Results and Discussion

Raw BR

The Greek raw BR consists of a mixed-phase assemblage of the total —Fe content (22.7 wt%), Al₂O₃ (23.6 wt%), SiO₂ (7.5 wt%), CaO (8.3 wt%), TiO₂ (5.1 wt%), and Na₂O (3.4 wt%) in the form of hematite/goethite, diaspore/boehmite/gibbsite, quartz, cancrinite, katoite, calcium carbonate, perovskite/anatase. The SEM–EDS analysis, as depicted in Fig. 1, conducted on the unprocessed BR, demonstrates the presence of sub-micron particles showcasing a complex combination of various major elements within the bulk composition of the sample. This intricate elemental association presents a substantial challenge in the context of metal recovery [12, 15].

Influence of H₂ Reduction Parameters on Metal Recovery

The reduction tests were performed by increasing the temperature from 400 to 700 °C for 120 min with the addition of 20 wt.% NaOH under an atmosphere of 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ with 20 L/h flowrate.

Fig. 1 SEM-EDS analysis on the Greek raw BR

The recovery rates of Al and Na increased with rising temperature (Fig. 2). The Al recovery rose from 76.8% to 80%, and Na recovery climbed from 88% to 92.5%, attributed to the enhancement of water-leachable aluminates (NaAlO₂) phases. During the H₂ reduction process of BR, the added NaOH reacts first with Al and Si phases due to high reactivity than Fe. Eventually, the formed Al phase of soluble NaAlO₂ is endothermic and highly stable than Fe₃O₄ and with increasing temperature NaAlO₂ phase formation increases and overall, this phenomena is positively effect on Al recovery from BR [4, 6]. Conversely, the rise in temperature from 400 to 500 °C led to increased Fe recovery and TFe grade, followed by a decline at 700 °C (Fig. 2). This was due to enhanced reaction rates between hematite and magnetite. However, higher temperatures caused magnetite to convert into FeO with weaker magnetic properties, resulting in Fe losses during magnetic separation [9, 12].

Experiments were conducted under a reduction temperature of 600 °C for 30–120 min, employing a gas mixture of 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ (flowrate: 20 L/h), and 20 wt.% NaOH. As depicted in Fig. 3, following water leaching and wet-magnetic separation, prolonged reduction times corresponded to slightly increased recovery rates for Al (79.4 to 81.5%) and Na (88.9 to 91.4%). Similarly, Fe recovery rates are enhanced from 69.8 to 74.7%, accompanied by an upsurge in the TFe grade of the magnetic concentrate (38.3 to 40%). Notably, a shorter reduction (30 min) exhibited the presence of unreduced hematite leading to Fe recovery/TFe grade (due to the low magnetic susceptibility of hematite).

Another set of experiments was conducted at 600 °C for 120 min using a 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ gas mixture and 20 L/h flowrate, with NaOH concentration varying from 10 to 25 wt.% (Fig. 4). Increasing NaOH addition to BR for H₂ reduction resulted in notable improvements in Al and Na

Fig. 2 Effect of Temperature (400–700 °C) on recovery of Fe, Al, and Na from H₂ reduced products (reduction condition: reduced pellet samples at 400–700 °C for 120 min with 20 wt.% NaOH under 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ [flowrate = 20 L/h])

Fig. 3 Effect of Time (30–120 min) on recovery of Fe, Al, and Na from H₂ reduced products (reduction condition: reduced pellet samples at 600 °C for 30–120 min with 20 wt.% NaOH under 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ [flowrate = 20 L/h])

Fig. 4 Effect of NaOH (10–25 wt.%) on recovery of Fe, Al, and Na from H₂ reduced products (reduction condition: reduced pellet samples at 600 °C for 120 min under 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ [flowrate = 20 L/h])

recovery rates (Al recovery rose from 62.6% to 81.8%, and Na recovery increased from 77.3% to 92.4%). This higher NaOH content facilitated the formation of sodium aluminate phases, enhancing Al and Na recovery, which aligns with findings from prior studies [16]. Conversely, Fe recovery exhibited different trends (Fig. 4). It increased from 68.6% to 74.7% (with an increase in TFe from 36.2% to 40%) from 10 to 20 wt.% NaOH but dropped to 57% (with a TFe Grade of 37.9%) at 25 wt.% NaOH due to an unfavorable water-leachable sodium iron oxide (NaFeO₂) phase formation [5, 6]. The development of a dense NaFeO₂ layer results in a slower reaction, hindering the conversion of hematite into magnetite. This layer forms a dense film that obstructs H₂ diffusion, thereby impeding the reduction of internal hematite [17, 18]. This phenomenon could potentially influence Fe conversion, subsequently affecting Fe-recovery outcomes.

Optimization and Validation of Process

Through a comprehensive factorial design involving a series of experimental runs (Table 1) and employing quadratic models, the process parameters for simultaneous Fe, Al, and Na extraction were optimized. The resultant optimized conditions (Fig. 5) encompass a reduction temperature of 600 °C, 20 wt.% NaOH, and a reduction time of 120 min. According to projections, the anticipated recoveries are 82.8% for Al, 70.5% for Fe, and 92.6% for Na.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) by using quadratic models employed in evaluating input process parameters (temperature, time, and NaOH) effect on Fe, Al, and Na recovery. From ANOVA analysis, a “Probability > F (with noise)” value below 0.05 resembles the statistical significance of the model terms. Under this condition ($P < 0.05$),

Fig. 5 Overlay plots from JMP design expert software indicating the optimal region for the simultaneous extraction of Fe, Al, and Na

the quadratic terms x_1^2 (temperature) and x_3^2 (NaOH addition) are more significant model terms for Fe recovery than the time factor. The model terms of linear x_3 and quadratic x_3^2 (NaOH) are more significant than time and temperature for the Al and Na recovery. Overall, temperature and NaOH addition parameters significantly influence the enhancement of simultaneous recovery of Fe, Al, and Na over time. According to the data presented in Table 2, the actual recovery rates for Fe, Al, and Na are 74.7%, 81.5%, and 91.4%, respectively. The deviations in Fe, Al, and Na recoveries are 4.2%, 1.4%, and 1.2%, respectively. A comparison between the projected and actual outcomes reveals that the optimal process parameters obtained using the software employed are remarkably accurate, with all values falling within an acceptable deviation threshold (<5%).

Table 2 Predicted and actual Fe, Al, and Na recovery values at optimized parameters (reduction temperature: 600 °C, NaOH addition: 20 wt.%, and reduction time: 120 min)

Item	Fe recovery (%)	Range in Fe recovery (%)	Al recovery (%)	Range in Al recovery (%)	Na recovery (%)	Range in Na recovery (%)
Predicted	70.5	54–72	82.9	79–86.5	92.6	90–94.5
Actual	74.7	–	81.5	–	91.4	–
Deviation	–4.2	–	–1.4	–	–1.2	–

The proposed process (Fig. 6) involves a two-stage method for recovering various products from BR. It includes H₂ reduction followed by water leaching and magnetic separation to obtain iron, sodium aluminate, and a non-magnetic fraction enriched in Ca, Si, and Ti as major products. The non-magnetic fraction holds the potential for recovering Ti, Si, REEs, and materials suitable for the construction industry. Moreover, alumina can be further extracted via precipitation for sale at higher market values, while the magnetic fraction finds applications as a pigment, and additive in iron-making, and sintering processes. Considering material balance (Fig. 6), processing 1 ton of BR yields 477 kg of magnetic fraction, 75 kg of non-magnetic fraction, and 477 kg of sodium aluminate/alumina after a 2-stage process of H₂ reduction (600 °C) followed by a combined water leaching-magnetic separation.

Conclusions

As an alternative, considering the low rates of utilization and the issues related to landfilling, extracting metals from bauxite residue (BR) emerges as the preferred option. The method reported in this paper employs H₂ reduction followed by water leaching and wet-magnetic separation to achieve simultaneous Fe, Al, and Na recovery, alongside the generation of a non-magnetic fraction enriched in Si, Ca, Ti, and REEs. Utilizing factorial design experiments and response surface methodology, optimal conditions were determined: a reduction temperature of 600 °C, a reduction time of 120 min, and a 20 wt.% NaOH addition. These parameters, facilitated by a lower amount of H₂ gas and reduction atmosphere of 5 vol.% H₂ + 95 vol.% N₂ with a 20 L/h flowrate, yielded impressive recoveries: Fe (74.7% with a grade of 40%), Al (81.5%), and Na (91.4%). The proposed process holds the promise of industrial-scale implementation due to simultaneous metal recovery with its nearly zero-waste discharge and sustainable nature, offering a transformative solution for BR processing as compared to existing methods.

Fig. 6 Summarized process flowsheet of extraction of values recovery from H₂ reduced BR

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